

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**A REVIEW ON AWARENESS AND CURRENT KNOWLEDGE
OF BREAST CANCER****Miss. Dhadan Sameera^{1*}, Mrs. U. Nirupama², Dr. K. Venugopal³**¹Final year B Pharmacy, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati – 517 506.²Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis & Quality assurance, Krishna Teja Pharmacy, College, Tirupati – 517 506.³Professor and Principal, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati – 517 506.**Abstract:**

Breast cancer is one of the most prevalent malignancies affecting women worldwide, resulting from abnormal cell growth in breast tissue due to a combination of internal factors genetics, hormonal changes and external influences lifestyle, environmental exposure. Risk factors include age, family history, obesity, alcohol consumption, and sedentary behavior: Breast cancer has historical accounts since ancient times however, the discussions around it were always prohibited, a situation that limited the process of early detection and diagnosis. The late 19th century brought about radical mastectomy, where improvements in survival rates resulted but at the cost of disfiguring the women involved. Today, breast cancer is classified into non-invasive and invasive. Public awareness campaigns have been crucial in promoting early detection through regular screenings like mammograms and self-examinations, significantly improving survival rates. Current treatment approaches include surgery, radiation, chemotherapy, hormonal therapy, targeted therapy, and immunotherapy. Despite advancements, challenges remain, such as cultural stigma, misinformation, and access to care. Efforts to increase awareness and education focus on risk reduction, emphasizing healthy lifestyle choices and regular screenings. Future strategies will likely involve personalized screening, genomic research, and community engagement to address disparities in breast cancer care. Ultimately, the aim is to enhance public knowledge, promote early detection, and improve access to care, thereby reducing breast cancer incidence and mortality rates.

Key Words: Breast cancer, Risk factors, Mammography, Immunotherapy, Genetics, Treatment, Early detection, Personalized medicine.

Corresponding author:**Dhadan Sameera,**

Final year B Pharmacy,

Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati – 517 506.

QR code

Please cite this article in press **Dhadan Sameera et al., A Review On Awareness And Current Knowledge Of Breast Cancer., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (11).**

1.INTRODUCTION:

One of the most prevalent malignancies impacting women globally is breast cancer. It originates when abnormal changes occur in the cells of the breast, leading to uncontrolled cell growth. This can result from a combination of internal factors, such as genetics and hormonal changes, as well as external factors. Poor lifestyle choices, like unhealthy diet, lack of physical activity, and alcohol consumption, contribute to the risk. Environmental factors, including exposure to certain chemicals or radiation, also play a role. Additionally, psychological and social stress can influence the body's immune response, potentially increasing vulnerability to breast cancer. Early detection and lifestyle modifications can help reduce the risk and improve outcomes. A cancerous tumor, composed of abnormal and rapidly dividing cancer cells, can invade and destroy surrounding healthy tissue and spread to other parts of the body through the lymphatic system or bloodstream, a process known as metastasis. In the case of breast cancer, it often begins in the cells lining the milk ducts, which are the channels that transport milk from the milk-producing glands (lobules) to the nipple.

Breast cancer has been known to mankind since ancient times. It has been mentioned in almost every period of record history. Because of the visible symptoms especially at later stages the lumps that progress tumours have been recorded by physicians from early times. This is more so because, unlike other internal cancers, lumps tend to manifest themselves as visible tumours.

Earlier, however it was a matter of taboo and embarrassment that meant detection and diagnosis was rare. The mention of breast cancers in literature beyond medical journals and books was rare. Involvement of more women and actively bringing out the disease into the open is a recent phenomenon that is around three or four decades old. In the 1990s the symbol of breast cancer- the pink ribbon- brought out a revolution against this cancer.

BREAST CANCER IN THE 17TH AND 18TH CENTURY:

Until the 17th century, Galen's humoral theory of breast cancer, which attributed the disease to an excess of black bile, was widely accepted. However, in 1680, French physician Francois de la Beo Sylvius challenged this notion, proposing that cancer resulted from a chemical process in which lymphatic fluids turned acidic and then acrid. By the 1730s, Paris physician Claude-Deshais Gendron also rejected Galen's systemic theory, suggesting that cancer arose

from a mix of nerve and glandular tissue with lymph vessels.

In 1713, Bernardino Ramazzini made a notable observation regarding the high incidence of breast cancer among nuns, hypothesizing that their lack of sexual activity contributed to cancer development. He suggested that without regular sex, reproductive organs, including the breast, could decay and lead to cancer. Another theory from Friedrich Hoffman of Prussia argued that women who had regular sexual activity but still developed cancer were practicing "vigorous" sex, which he believed could cause lymphatic blockages.

In 1757, Henri Le Dran, a prominent French physician, introduced the idea that breast cancer could be treated through surgery. He suggested that the tumor should be surgically removed, along with any infected lymph nodes in the armpits, to prevent the spread of the disease. This marked a significant shift in breast cancer treatment. Claude-Nicolas Le Cat supported this approach, arguing that surgery was the only effective method to treat breast cancer. This belief persisted into the 20th century, leading to the development of the radical mastectomy, an extensive surgical procedure that involved the complete removal of the breast and surrounding tissues.

THE 19TH AND 20TH CENTURY:

By the mid-19th century, surgery had become the primary treatment option for breast cancer. Advancements in medical practices, such as the development of antiseptic techniques, anesthesia, and blood transfusions, significantly improved the chances of survival after surgery. These innovations reduced the risk of infection, made the procedures less painful, and helped patients recover more successfully, making surgery a more viable option for treating breast cancer during this period.

William Halsted of New York revolutionized breast cancer surgery in the late 19th century by developing the radical mastectomy, a procedure that became the gold standard for nearly 100 years. This surgery involved the removal of the breast, axillary lymph nodes, and chest muscles in a single "en bloc" procedure to prevent the spread of cancer. Radical mastectomy dominated breast cancer treatment during the first four decades of the 20th century. While it improved survival rates, especially when performed early, it left many women disfigured and with significant side effects like a deformed chest wall, lymphedema (arm swelling due to lymph node removal), and chronic pain. As a result, many women

hesitated to choose the surgery despite its life-saving potential.

In 1895, Scottish surgeon George Beatson made a groundbreaking discovery: removing the ovaries in a patient with breast cancer led to a reduction in tumor size. This was due to the ovaries' production of estrogen, which fueled tumor growth. This discovery led to the practice of removing both ovaries, along with a radical mastectomy, to slow the cancer's progression.

However, even in women without ovaries, estrogen could still be produced by the adrenal glands. In 1952, Charles Huggins introduced adrenalectomy, the removal of the adrenal glands, as a method to further starve tumors of estrogen. Building on this, surgeons Rolf Leffert and Herbert Olivecrona began removing the pituitary gland, which also played a role in stimulating estrogen production, to combat breast cancer. These developments marked early efforts to understand and target the hormonal basis of breast cancer.

Not all changes in breast cells lead to cancer. Some non-cancerous (benign) conditions, like atypical hyperplasia (a precancerous condition where cells grow abnormally) and cysts (fluid-filled sacs), can develop due to cellular changes but do not spread to other parts of the body or invade nearby tissues. However, some of these conditions may increase the risk of developing breast cancer later. Ductal carcinoma refers to breast cancer that originates in the cells lining the milk ducts. It is one of the most common forms of breast cancer. Similarly, lobular carcinoma develops in the cells of the lobules, which are the clusters of glands responsible for producing milk. Both ductal and lobular carcinomas can exist in an early stage known as *in situ* (DCIS for ductal carcinoma in situ and LCIS for lobular carcinoma in situ). Detecting carcinoma in situ early is crucial, as it can often be treated before progressing to invasive cancer.

Breast cancer is most commonly diagnosed in women between the ages of 50 and 69, and early detection significantly improves the chances of survival. One of the key factors contributing to breast cancer risk is prolonged exposure to the hormones estrogen and progesterone. These hormones, especially estrogen, are linked to breast cancer development by promoting the growth of breast cells, which can lead to mutations over time. As women age, their risk of developing breast cancer increases, with higher incidence rates observed in high-income, developed countries such as Canada, the United States, and several European

nations. This increased prevalence is likely due to a combination of lifestyle, genetic, and environmental factors, as well as access to more advanced healthcare and diagnostic tools in these regions. Understanding these risk factors and promoting awareness is essential for effective prevention and early diagnosis.

2. AIM AND OBJECTIVES:

Aim: To enhance public knowledge and understanding of breast cancer, promote early detection through education and screening initiatives, and foster community support, ultimately reducing the incidence and mortality rates associated with the disease.

Objectives:

1. **Increase Awareness:** Educate the public about breast cancer risk factors, symptoms, and the importance of regular screenings through community outreach programs and campaigns.
2. **Promote Screening:** Encourage regular mammograms and clinical breast exams, particularly among high-risk populations, to facilitate early detection.
3. **Enhance Education:** Provide accessible, accurate information about breast cancer, its treatment options, and available support resources to empower patients and their families.
4. **Support Research:** Advocate for funding and support for breast cancer research to develop better treatment methods, enhance prevention strategies, and improve patient outcomes.
5. **Improve Access to Care:** Work towards reducing barriers to healthcare services, including screenings and treatments, particularly in underserved communities.

3. TYPES OF BREAST CANCER:

Basically, breast cancers are of 2 different types as Non-invasive breast cancer & Invasive breast cancer.

- **Non- invasive breast cancer:(2 types)**

Cancer that are contained within the milk ducts or lobules in the breast. Treatment options typically include surgery (lumpectomy or mastectomy) and may be followed by radiation therapy to reduce recurrence risk.

These are of 2 types:

1. Ductal carcinoma in situ (DCIS):

Ductal carcinoma in situ (DCIS) is an early, non-invasive form of breast cancer where abnormal cells are confined to the milk ducts and haven't spread to surrounding tissue. It is often detected during routine mammograms, usually showing as microcalcifications. Treatment options include surgery, radiation, and sometimes hormone therapy, depending on the case. The prognosis is excellent when treated early, but without treatment, it could potentially progress to invasive breast cancer.

Fig:1 Ductal carcinoma in situ (DCIS)

2.Lobular carcinoma in situ (LCIS):

Lobular carcinoma in situ (LCIS) is a non-invasive breast condition where abnormal cells are found in the milk-producing lobules. While not cancer, LCIS increases the risk of developing invasive breast cancer later. It typically shows no symptoms and is often discovered incidentally during biopsies for other issues. Management may include regular monitoring, medications to reduce cancer risk, or preventive surgery depending on individual risk factors.

Fig:2 Lobular carcinoma in situ (LCIS)

- **Invasive Breast Cancer (7 types):** This type of cancer spreads from the breast ducts or lobules into the surrounding breast tissue, allowing it to potentially spread to other parts of the body.

Type-1, Invasive ductal carcinoma (IDC):

Invasive ductal carcinoma (IDC) is the most common type of breast cancer, where cancer cells start in the milk ducts and invade surrounding breast tissue. It can also spread to other parts of the body. IDC may present as a lump in the breast, changes in breast shape, or skin dimpling, though it can also be asymptomatic. Treatment typically involves surgery, radiation, chemotherapy, hormone therapy, or targeted therapy, depending on the stage and characteristics of the tumor.

Type-2, Invasive lobular carcinoma (ILC):

Invasive lobular carcinoma (ILC) is a type of breast cancer that begins in the milk-producing lobules and spreads to surrounding breast tissue. It often grows in a subtle, diffuse pattern, making it harder to detect on mammograms or through physical exams. Symptoms may include a thickening or fullness in the breast rather than a defined lump. Treatment options typically include surgery, radiation, chemotherapy, hormone therapy, or targeted therapy based on the stage and features of the cancer.

Type-3, Paget Disease of the Breast: A rare cancer that typically starts in the ducts of the breast and spreads to the skin of the nipple and areola, characterized by redness, crusting, or flaking.

Type-4, Inflammatory Breast Cancer (IBC): An aggressive and rare type that blocks lymph vessels in the skin of the breast, leading to redness, swelling, and an inflamed appearance.

Type-5, Phyllodes Tumor: A rare type of tumor that forms in the connective tissue (stroma) of the breast, including ducts and lobules, and can be either benign or malignant.

Type-6, Locally advanced breast cancer (LABC):

LABC is an invasive breast cancer that is large or has spread beyond the breast to other nearby areas such as the skin, chest wall or muscle and may have extensive local lymph node involvement.

Type-7, Metastatic breast cancer (MBC):

Metastatic breast cancer, also known as stage 4 breast cancer. This type of breast cancer has spread to more distant parts of the body such as the bones, liver, lungs, or brain.

Fig:3 Metastatic breast cancer

4. RISK FACTORS OF BREAST CANCER:

Breast cancer risk factors include being female, advancing age, and a family history of breast cancer, particularly with BRCA1/BRCA2 gene mutations. Lifestyle factors, including obesity, alcohol consumption, smoking, and lack of physical activity, also contribute. Women who have not had children or had their first child after 30 face higher risk. Previous radiation exposure and high breast density further elevate the risk. Early detection and adopting healthy habits can help mitigate these risks.

4.1NON-MODIFIABLE FACTORS:

- **Gender:** Being female significantly increases the risk of developing breast cancer.
- **Age:** The risk of breast cancer increases with age, particularly after age 50.
- **Family History:** Having close relatives (mother, sister, daughter) with breast cancer raises the likelihood of developing the disease.
- **Genetic Mutations:** Inherited mutations, such as BRCA1 and BRCA2, greatly increase the risk.
- **Personal History of Breast Cancer:** Women who have had breast cancer are at higher risk of recurrence or developing new cancers.
- **Dense Breast Tissue:** High breast density is linked to a higher risk of breast cancer.
- **Early Menstruation/Late Menopause:** Early onset of menstruation (before age 12)

or late menopause (after age 55) increases lifetime exposure to estrogen, raising the risk

4.2MODIFIABLE FACTORS:

- **Alcohol Consumption:** Drinking alcohol increases the risk of breast cancer, even at moderate levels.
- **Obesity:** Being overweight or obese, especially after menopause, raises the risk due to increased estrogen production in fat tissue.
- **Physical Inactivity:** A sedentary lifestyle is associated with a higher risk of breast cancer.
- **Smoking:** Smoking, particularly long-term, may increase the risk of breast cancer.
- **Hormone Replacement Therapy (HRT):** Long-term use of combined estrogen and progesterone therapy during menopause can raise the risk.
- **Reproductive Choices:** Having children at a younger age, breastfeeding, and avoiding late pregnancies can lower the risk.
- **Diet:** A healthy diet rich in fruits, vegetables, and fiber may reduce breast cancer risk.

5.STAGES OF BREAST CANCER:

The staging process is crucial for tailoring treatment plans and understanding prognosis. Each stage reflects different characteristics of the cancer, influencing decisions around surgery, chemotherapy, radiation, and other therapies. It's also important for determining eligibility for clinical trials, as some studies focus on specific stages of cancer.

The TNM staging system, overseen by the American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC), provides a standardized way to classify and communicate breast cancer. This system focuses on three main clinical characteristics:

T (Tumor): This indicates the size of the tumor and whether it has invaded nearby tissues.

N (Nodes): This reflects whether the cancer has spread to nearby lymph nodes.

M (Metastasis): This indicates whether the cancer has spread to distant parts of the body.

Each characteristic is assigned a number or letter to provide more specific details, with higher numbers indicating more advanced cancer. For instance, T1 might represent a small tumor, while T4 indicates a larger tumor with significant local invasion. Similarly,

N1 might mean minimal lymph node involvement, while N3 indicates extensive spread to lymph nodes. The M category helps assess whether the cancer has metastasized to distant organs. This systematic approach ensures that healthcare providers can consistently classify cancer, facilitating comparison of treatment outcomes across different patients and settings.

5.1 STAGE 0 BREAST CANCER:

Stage 0 breast cancer, such as DCIS (ductal carcinoma in situ), is a non-invasive condition where cancer cells are confined to the ducts of the breast and have not spread to surrounding tissues. This stage is often detected through mammograms and may not present noticeable symptoms. Early detection is key, and treatment options can include surgery, radiation, and hormone therapy, depending on individual cases.

5.2 STAGE 1 BREAST CANCER:

Stage I breast cancer is characterized by the early invasion of cancer cells into surrounding breast tissue, and it's divided into two subcategories: IA and IB.

Stage IA involves:

- A tumor that measures up to 2 centimeters (cm).
- No spread to lymph nodes; cancer is confined to the breast

Stage IB involves:

- No visible tumor in the breast, but small groups of cancer cells (larger than 0.2 mm but not larger than 2 mm) are found in the lymph nodes.
- Alternatively, there can be a tumor up to 2 cm in the breast, accompanied by small groups of cancer cells in the lymph nodes

If stage IB breast cancer is also estrogen receptor-positive or progesterone receptor-positive, it may be reclassified as stage IA, as these characteristics indicate a less aggressive form of cancer.

Microscopic invasion can occur in this stage, where cancer cells begin to invade tissue outside the duct or lobule, but the invasive cells measure no more than 1 mm.

5.3 STAGE II BREAST CANCER:

Stage II breast cancer is divided into two subcategories, IIA and IIB. Stage IIA is characterized by several conditions: either no detectable tumor in the breast, but cancer larger than 2 mm is found in one to three axillary lymph nodes or in lymph nodes near the breast bone; a tumor that measures 2 cm or smaller that has spread to the axillary lymph nodes; or a tumor larger than 2 cm but not exceeding 5 cm, with no spread to

the axillary lymph nodes. This stage indicates a more extensive involvement than Stage I, particularly with the potential for lymph node involvement, which plays a crucial role in determining treatment options and prognosis.

Doctors classify breast cancer stages based on a combination of tumor size, lymph node involvement, and specific biological factors. For instance, a tumor measuring between 2 and 5 cm may be categorized as stage IIA if it hasn't spread to lymph nodes or distant parts of the body, is HER2-negative, or as stage IA if it meets additional criteria, including being estrogen receptor-positive and having a low Oncotype DX Recurrence Score. Stage IIB is characterized by a tumor larger than 2 cm but no larger than 5 cm with either small groups of cancer cells in the lymph nodes or spread to one to three axillary lymph nodes. However, even if a tumor fits the size criteria for stage IIB, it might still be classified as stage I if it is HER2-positive and hormone receptor-positive. These classifications help guide treatment decisions and prognostic considerations.

5.4 STAGE III BREAST CANCER:

Stage IIIA breast cancer is characterized by specific conditions related to tumor size and lymph node involvement. In this stage, there may be no detectable tumor in the breast, or any size tumor could be present, but cancer is found in 4 to 9 axillary lymph nodes or in lymph nodes near the breastbone. Additionally, if the tumor is larger than 5 cm, small groups of cancer cells (ranging from larger than 0.2 mm to not larger than 2 mm) can be found in the lymph nodes. Alternatively, cancer may have spread to 1 to 3 axillary lymph nodes or lymph nodes near the breastbone. This stage indicates a significant progression of the disease and often requires more aggressive treatment approaches.

Cancer staging is crucial for determining treatment and prognosis, assessed through the TNM system, which evaluates tumor size (T), lymph node involvement (N), and metastasis (M). Stage 0 indicates non-invasive cancer, while stages I-IV describe increasing severity and spread, with stage IV being metastatic. The American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC) guidelines now also consider tumor grade, hormone receptor status, and HER2 status, making staging more nuanced. For example, stage I includes small tumors that haven't spread, while stage II involves larger tumors or lymph node involvement. Stage III cancers may invade nearby tissues and lymph nodes, and stage IV cancers have spread to distant organs. Understanding these stages helps guide treatment decisions and patient outcomes.

5.5. STAGE IV BEAST CANCER:

Stage IV breast cancer, also known as metastatic breast cancer, is indeed a serious condition. It indicates that the cancer has spread beyond the breast and nearby lymph nodes to distant organs. This can significantly affect treatment options and prognosis.

There are two scenarios for Stage IV: it can be diagnosed initially (de novo) or as a recurrence of a previous breast cancer. Treatment often focuses on managing the disease, improving quality of life, and prolonging survival.

6. PUBLIC AWARENESS OF BREAST CANCER:

Public awareness of breast cancer is vital for improving early detection, treatment, and outcomes. Awareness campaigns aim to educate individuals about the importance of regular screenings, such as mammograms and self-examinations, which can lead to earlier diagnoses when the disease is most treatable. These initiatives highlight common symptoms, including lumps, changes in breast shape or size, and unusual skin texture or discharge, encouraging women to seek medical advice promptly.

Education on risk factors plays a key role in awareness efforts. Individuals learn about non-modifiable factors, such as age, family history, and genetic mutations (e.g., BRCA1 and BRCA2), alongside modifiable factors like obesity, alcohol consumption, and physical inactivity. This public knowledge empowers people to make healthier lifestyle choices that may reduce their risk of developing breast cancer.

Global campaigns, including Breast Cancer Awareness Month, utilize the pink ribbon symbol to foster community involvement and support for research and funding. They also provide platforms for survivors to share their stories, helping to destigmatize the disease and create a supportive network. Ultimately, enhanced public awareness leads to increased screenings, earlier detection, improved treatment outcomes, and a stronger community committed to fighting breast cancer together.

7. EARLY DETECTION AND SCREENING:

7.1 Screening Methods:

- **Mammography:** Recommended for women starting at age 40, or earlier for those with risk factors. It can detect tumors that are too small to be felt.
- **Clinical Breast Exam (CBE):** A physical exam by a healthcare professional, usually part of routine check-ups.

- **Breast Self-Exam (BSE):** Women should be aware of their breast tissue and report any changes, although BSE alone is not a substitute for professional screenings.

7.2 Importance of Early Detection:

- **Higher Survival Rates:** Early-stage breast cancer (Stage 0 or I) has a much higher survival rate compared to later stages.
- **Less Aggressive Treatment:** Detecting cancer early may allow for less invasive treatments, such as lumpectomy instead of mastectomy.

7.3 Risk Factors:

- **Genetics:** Family history and genetic mutations (e.g., BRCA1, BRCA2) significantly increase risk.
- **Lifestyle Factors:** Obesity, alcohol consumption, and sedentary lifestyle are associated with higher risk.
- **Age:** Risk increases as women age, particularly after 55.

7.4 Follow-Up:

- **Additional Testing:** If a screening shows abnormal results, further tests such as ultrasound, MRI, or biopsy may be required for diagnosis.

7.5 Technological Advances:

- **3D Mammography:** Provides more detailed images and reduces false positives, allowing for better detection of breast cancer.

8. FUTURE PROSPECTIVE:

Future directions in breast cancer awareness and education:

Future directions in breast cancer awareness and education are set to transform how we approach screening, prevention, and treatment. One promising area is personalized screening, where enhanced risk-based protocols will consider genetic, familial, and environmental factors to create tailored screening schedules for individuals. This individualized approach is complemented by genomic advances, which are deepening our understanding of cancer predisposition. As researchers unravel the genetic underpinnings of breast cancer, early detection and targeted prevention strategies will become more refined. Additionally, precision medicine is revolutionizing treatment by utilizing individual genetic profiles to inform therapy choices, allowing for more effective and less invasive options. The ongoing development of immunotherapy, particularly

cancer vaccines and immune-based therapies, holds promise for innovative prevention and treatment modalities

Moreover, integrating lifestyle factors into breast cancer prevention will emphasize the importance of healthier habits among women, further contributing to overall well-being. The rise of digital health tools, including mobile apps and wearable technology, will enable individuals to monitor their health more effectively and facilitate early detection of potential issues. Drug repositioning is another exciting avenue, as researchers explore existing medications for new applications in cancer treatment, potentially providing quicker access to effective therapies. Finally, community engagement will play a crucial role in increasing awareness and education, particularly in diverse populations, helping to address disparities in breast cancer care and ensuring that all women receive the information and resources they need to make informed health decisions.

9.CURRENT TREATMENT APPROACHES IN BREAST CANCER:

- **Surgery:** This may involve lumpectomy (removing the tumor) or mastectomy (removing one or both breasts), depending on the stage and type of cancer.

Eg:Mammoplasty,Mastectomy,Lumpectomy,Lymph node dissection.

- **Radiation Therapy:** Often used after surgery to eliminate remaining cancer cells, particularly in the breast area or lymph nodes.

Eg:Fluorouracil,Kinase inhibitors,Lapatinib,Neratinib

- **Chemotherapy:** Uses drugs to kill cancer cells and is often employed before surgery (neoadjuvant) or after (adjuvant) to reduce recurrence risk.

Eg: Anthracyclines, Taxanes,5-fluorouracil, Capecitabine, Cyclophosphamide

- **Hormonal Therapy:** For hormone receptor-positive cancers, medications like tamoxifen or aromatase inhibitors can help block hormones that fuel tumor growth.

Eg:Anastrozole,Tamoxifen,Fulvestrant

- **Targeted Therapy:** Treatments such as trastuzumab (Herceptin) are used for HER2-positive cancers, targeting specific pathways involved in cancer growth
Eg:Trastuzumab,Olaparib

- **Immunotherapy:** An emerging approach that helps the immune system recognize and fight cancer cells, particularly for triple-negative breast cancer.Eg:Pembrolizumab,Trastuzumab
- **Clinical Trials:** Patients may participate in trials for new treatments or combinations of existing therapies.

Fig:4 Global Breast Cancer Market

10.CHALLENGES IN INCREASING BREAST CANCER AWARENESS:

Cultural sensitivity is essential in addressing breast cancer awareness and education, as varying cultural beliefs and stigmas can significantly hinder open discussions about the disease. In many communities, cultural norms may discourage conversations about health issues, particularly those related to cancer. This can lead to misunderstandings and reluctance to seek help, ultimately affecting early detection and treatment outcomes. Tailoring educational efforts to respect and incorporate cultural beliefs is vital for fostering a supportive environment where individuals feel comfortable discussing breast cancer and exploring prevention options.

Misinformation poses another significant challenge in the realm of breast cancer awareness. The proliferation of inaccurate information through social media and other platforms can create confusion about risk factors, screening guidelines, and treatment options. This can result in individuals making uninformed decisions about their health or dismissing the importance of screenings altogether. To combat this issue, it is crucial to provide clear, evidence-based information and engage trusted community leaders who can help disseminate accurate knowledge, ensuring that individuals receive the right guidance and support.

Access to resources is a persistent barrier, particularly in underserved communities where healthcare

disparities are prevalent. Limited availability of screening programs, educational materials, and healthcare facilities can prevent individuals from taking proactive steps in their breast cancer care. Moreover, socioeconomic challenges often exacerbate these issues, as many individuals prioritize immediate needs over preventive care. Fragmented messaging from numerous organizations can further dilute the impact of awareness efforts, making it difficult for the public to understand the urgency of breast cancer prevention. Capturing and maintaining public interest in awareness campaigns is essential, as a crowded health landscape can easily overshadow the importance of breast cancer education, necessitating innovative approaches to engage communities effectively.

11. PREVENTION AND RISK REDUCTION STRATEGIES:

Adopting healthy lifestyle choices plays a crucial role in reducing the risk of developing breast cancer. Maintaining a healthy weight, engaging in regular physical activity, and consuming a balanced diet rich in fruits, vegetables, whole grains, and lean proteins can significantly enhance overall health and lower cancer risk. Additionally, limiting alcohol consumption to no more than one drink per day and avoiding tobacco and second-hand smoke are important preventative measures. Regular screenings, including mammograms and clinical breast exams, are essential for early detection, while women with a family history of breast cancer should consider genetic counseling and testing for BRCA1 and BRCA2 mutations to assess their risk.

For those identified as high-risk, discussing preventive medications such as selective estrogen receptor modulators with a healthcare provider can be beneficial. Surgical options, including prophylactic mastectomy or oophorectomy, may also be considered in certain cases. It is important to discuss hormonal factors, particularly regarding hormone replacement therapy after menopause, to ensure informed decisions are made. Additionally, breastfeeding, when possible, has been shown to slightly reduce breast cancer risk, and minimizing unnecessary radiation exposure, especially during adolescence, is advisable. Implementing these strategies, alongside regular consultations with healthcare providers for personalized advice, can significantly lower the risk of breast cancer and promote overall well-being.

12. CONCLUSION:

Breast cancer remains a significant global health challenge, influenced by a mix of genetic, hormonal, and lifestyle factors. While historical treatment

methods, such as radical mastectomy, improved survival rates, they often resulted in physical and emotional scars. Today, advancements in classification and treatment ranging from surgery to immunotherapy offer hope for better outcomes. Public awareness initiatives have played a pivotal role in promoting early detection through regular screenings and self-examinations, leading to improved survival rates. However, barriers such as cultural stigma, misinformation, and disparities in access to care persist. The future of breast cancer management will likely focus on personalized approaches, genomic research, and community engagement to enhance education and support. By prioritizing awareness and proactive health choices, we can reduce the incidence and mortality associated with breast cancer, fostering a more informed and healthier society. Continued efforts are essential to ensure equitable access to care for all women affected by this disease.

13. REFERENCES:

1. Obeagu EI, Babar Q, Vincent CC, et al. Therapeutic targets in breast cancer signaling: a review. *J Pharm Res Int.* 2021;33:82–99.
2. Aizaz M, Khan M, Khan FI, et al. Burden of breast cancer: developing countries perspective. *Int J Innov Appl Res.* 2023; 11:31–7.
3. Ibekwe AM, Obeagu EI, Ibekwe CE, et al. Challenges of exclusive breastfeeding among working class women in a teaching hospital South East, Nigeria. *J Pharm Res Int.* 2022;34:1.
4. Edward U, Obeagu EI, Okorie HM, et al. Studies of serum calcium, inorganic phosphate, and magnesium levels in lactating mothers in Owerri. *J Pharm Res Int.* 2021;33:209–16.
5. Obeagu EI, Ahmed YA, Obeagu GU, et al. Biomarkers of breast cancer: overview. *Int J Curr Res Biol Med.* 2023;8:8–16.
6. Iatrakis G, Zervoudis S. Epidemiology of ductal carcinoma in situ. *Chirurgia (Romania).* 2021;116(5 Suppl):S15–S21.
7. Jagsi R, Mason G, Overmoyer BA, et al. Inflammatory breast cancer defined: proposed common diagnostic criteria to guide treatment and research. *Breast Cancer Res Treat.* 2022;192:235–43.
8. Pedersen RN, Esen BO, Mellemkjær L, et al. The incidence of breast cancer recurrence 10–32 years after primary diagnosis. *J Natl Cancer Inst.* 2022;114:391–99.
9. Van Ourti T, O'Donnell O, Koç H, et al. Effect of screening mammography on breast cancer mortality: Quasi-experimental evidence from the rollout of the Dutch population-based program with 17-year follow-up of a cohort. *Int J Cancer.* 2020;146:2201–8.
10. Buist DSM, Abraham L, Lee CI, et al. Breast biopsy intensity and findings following breast cancer

screening in women with and without a personal history of breast cancer. *JAMA Intern Med.* 2018;178:458–68.

11. Maio F, Tari DU, Granata V, et al. Breast cancer screening during COVID-19 emergency: patients and department management in a local experience. *J Pers Med.* 2021;11:380.

12. Li MR, Liu MZ, Ge YQ, et al. Assistance by routine CT features combined with 3D texture analysis in the diagnosis of BRCA gene mutation status in advanced epithelial ovarian cancer. *Front Oncol.* 2021;11:696780.

13. Hu X, Zhang Q, Xing W, et al. Role of microRNA/lncRNA intertwined with the Wnt/ β -Catenin axis in regulating the pathogenesis of triple negative breast cancer. *Front Pharmacol.* 2022;13:814971.

14. Thigpen D, Kappler A, Brem R. The role of ultrasound in screening dense breasts—a review of the literature and practical solutions for implementation. *Diagnostics.* 2018;8:20.

15. Vatankhah H, Khalili P, Vatanparast M, et al. Prevalence of early and late menopause and its determinants in Rafsanjan cohort study. *Sci Rep.* 2023;13:1847.

16. Garnæs KK, Elvebakk T, Salvesen O, et al. Dietary intake in early pregnancy and glycemia in late pregnancy among women with obesity. *Nutrients.* 2022;14:105.

17. Mills ZB, Faull RLM, Kwakowsky A. Is hormone replacement therapy a risk factor or a therapeutic

option for Alzheimer's disease? *Int J Mol Sci.* 2023;24:3205.

18. Kunyahamu MS, Daud A, Jusoh N. Obesity among health-care workers: which occupations are at higher risk of being obese? *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2021;18:4381.

19. Sharma, R. Global, regional, national burden of breast cancer in 185 countries: Evidence from GLOBOCAN 2018. *Breast Cancer Res. Treat.,* 2021; 187: 557–567.

20. Ferlay, J.; Ervik, M.; Lam, F.; Colombet, M.; Mery, L.; Piñeros, M.; Znaor, A.; Soerjomataram, I.; Bray, F. *Global Cancer Observatory: Cancer Today*; International Agency for Research on Cancer: Lyon, France, 2020; accessed on 9 July 2021

21. Sung, H.; Ferlay, J.; Siegel, R.L.; Laversanne, M.; Soerjomataram, I.; Jemal, A.; Bray, F. *Global Cancer Statistics 2020: GLOBOCAN Estimates of Incidence and Mortality Worldwide for 36 Cancers in 185 Countries.* *CA Cancer J. Clin.,* 2021; 71: 209–249.

22. Duggan, C.; Dvaladze, A.; Rositch, A.F.; Ginsburg, O.; Yip, C.; Horton, S.; Rodriguez, R.C.; Eniu, A.; Mutebi, M.; Bourque, J.; et al. *The Breast Health Global Initiative 2018 Global Summit on Improving Breast Healthcare Through Resource-Stratified Phased Implementation: Methods and overview.* *Cancer,* 2020; 126: 2339–2352.

23. World Health Organization. *Global Health Estimates 2016: Disease Burden by Cause, Age, Sex, by Country and By Region, 2000–2016*; World Health Organization: Geneva, Switzerland, 2018; accessed on 9 July 2021